

THIRTY-FIFTH ANNUAL REPORT 1991

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
THIRTY-FIFTH ANNUAL REPORT 1991

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The scholar at his book-wheel is a reproduction of an engraving in Agostino Ramelli's *Le diverse et artificiose machine...* Paris, 1588. It first appeared in the Council's third annual report, with the following explanation: "the picture symbolizes the interest of the Council on Library Resources in both the content of books and the mechanics of library service." The engraving has appeared in each annual report since that time.

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2. Resigned, November 1990.
3. Retired, December 1990.

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4. As of January 1991.

5. Resigned, May 1991.

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6. Elected at the November 1990 Directors' meeting.

Acknowledgements

The following foundations were among the supporters of Council activities during 1990/1991. All deserve the thanks of the library community.

The AT&T Foundation

The J. Paul Getty Trust

The W. K. Kellogg Foundation

The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation

The Pew Charitable Trusts

Chairman's Message

The year 1991 marks the thirty-fifth anniversary of the founding of the Council on Library Resources. The Council's third president, Warren J. Haas, retired on December 31, 1990, after thirteen years of distinguished service to the Council. It is therefore an appropriate moment to note that the many accomplishments of the Council in the thirty-five years of its existence, as summarized briefly in the Council's annual reports, are in large part the result of the insight, the perseverance, and the creativity of its presidents, guided by its board of directors.

The Ford Foundation acted with foresight when it established the Council in 1956. Remarkable technological, economic, and social changes in the nation's educational and research environments occurred during the next decades. The processes by which users organize, retrieve, and disseminate information changed dramatically. The Ford Foundation charged the Council "to aid in the solution of library problems; to conduct research in, develop and demonstrate new techniques and methods and to disseminate through any means the results thereof." The means to carry out this charge have been devised by the Council's presidents and its directors. Work has gone forward with the assistance of the many foundations that have provided the Council with financial support and with the collaboration of many in the library, academic, and information services communities.

Jim Haas was especially effective at enlisting the assistance of a broad segment of these communities. Two recent examples come to mind. Last year the Council oversaw the publication of a major statement about the future of academic research libraries that was based on discussions of the Research Library Committee, a group composed of senior librarians, scholars, and foundation and university officers. The work of the Committee was sponsored by the Council and three scholarly organizations, the American Council of Learned Societies, the Association of American Universities, and the Social Science Research Council. This year, an Advisory Committee on Library Education, a ten-member committee of library school deans, completed its discussions on improving the quality of library schools in research universities. A summary of the committee's recommendations is included in this annual report.

Such collaborative efforts were a hallmark of the substance and style Jim Haas brought to the Council. He was always concerned that planning for the future of libraries not take place in isolation from the ultimate users of library services. At the same time, he often expressed his conviction that librarians had fashioned an exceptional modern record in collaborative activity, resource sharing, and technological innovation, and that they had done so in advance of some other sectors of the research community. Much of the research that made this record possible was itself funded by the Council.

I am pleased to welcome W. David Penniman (most recently Director of the Information Services Group at AT&T Bell Laboratories) as the fourth president of the Council. The Council will continue to evolve in the years ahead under Dr. Penniman's leadership, building on the firm foundation established by Warren J. Haas and his predecessors Fred C. Cole and Verner W. Clapp.

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "Maximilian W. Kempner". The signature is written in a cursive, flowing style with a large initial 'M'.

Maximilian W. Kempner
Chairman

President's Message

As the fourth president of the Council on Library Resources, I have been presented with a challenge and an opportunity. The challenge is to follow an exceptional handful of leaders who have helped to make the Council a powerful mechanism for supporting the role that libraries play in our society. The opportunity is to extend the Council's interests to every aspect of information delivery service, in order to help libraries position themselves to remain the primary source of information delivery.

The environment in which libraries operate today is made increasingly complex by budget constraints, rising operating costs, higher demand for service, developing technologies, and a growing number of alternative information delivery systems. Clearly, new approaches to service delivery, internal processing, and organizational issues must be found.

The pressures facing libraries are such that change is essential if libraries are to continue to maintain the quality of their services. It is essential that we act to shape the future, not wait to let it shape us. For we face a paradox of change that is deceptively simple: in a changing environment one must change to remain stable. For libraries to remain a significant force, they must change; if they do not change, they will be unable to maintain their ability to serve.

The Council intends to continue to be a vital force for change in the library arena. But beyond that, the Council is also concerned with the broader issues faced by related information service providers, including computer centers, database services, bibliographic utilities, university presses, community information centers, and other facilities and services that are emerging as the information resources of the future.

Libraries themselves are unlike any other information services in that they strike a balance between content and channel. They are concerned with what is delivered as much as with the technology by which it is delivered. Libraries need to retain that emphasis on content while focusing more intently on information delivery, integrating into their mission the concerns of the broader communities in which they reside.

Libraries must be viewed as information delivery systems, not warehouses. In order to move the library community toward this view, we must change the motivation of those who manage libraries, and the problem of motivation rests with how the library leaders of today and tomorrow will be measured. If they continue to be measured on the basis of collection size, the number of staff supervised, or the number of computers and databases controlled, we will have static, unresponsive organizations that fail to serve their users as fully as they could. New measures of performance must be developed to help drive the change process, and library leaders themselves must develop these measures. They must choose a new philosophy of information service leadership.

My predecessor, Warren J. Haas, noted that the function of librarianship is to promote and continuously improve the ability of society, and of each individual, to make use of what has been previously learned or created. That process of continuous improvement calls for a willingness to commit to lifelong learning and development on the part of the library community as well; that commitment is especially true for its leaders. The Council is uniquely positioned as a fulcrum for change to help library leaders—and the library and information service community as a whole—to serve society to the fullest. The Council is committed to seeking out and funding those organizations and individuals who believe in the process of continuous improvement for libraries and the library profession. It is only through this commitment that we will enable society continually to reap the benefits that libraries can offer.

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "W. David Penniman". The signature is written in a cursive, flowing style with a large initial "W".

W. David Penniman
President

Program Review

CLR-Managed Projects

The Council's activities as an operating foundation involve projects for which it not only provides funds but enlists participants and serves as the secretariat. During fiscal 1991, several important projects culminated in Council publications, and another resulted in the award of four \$100,000 grants to research universities. These and other projects are described below. Participants in each of these projects are listed on pages 34-36.

Professional Education

Academic Library Management Intern Program

The Academic Library Management Intern Program is offered biennially by the Council for librarians who have an interest in the administration of large libraries and who wish to improve their management abilities. Interns typically spend the academic year working with the director and senior administrative staff of a large and well-managed research library. Individual programs vary, but all interns observe and participate in management activities and undertake special assignments. The goal of the program is to expose interns to the complex array of policy matters and operating problems of large research libraries.

The 1990-91 Academic Library Management Interns and their locations were Susan Klingberg, Princeton University; Margaret L. Morrison, University of Chicago; and Virginia Steel, Brown University. As fiscal 1991 ended, preparations were under way for the 1992-93 intern program.

CLR/Kellogg Fellows

In December 1990 the Council announced a new project to ease the growing shortage of library science educators by helping graduate students in the field finish their degrees more rapidly than they would without financial support. The W. K. Kellogg Foundation of Battle Creek, Michigan, is sponsoring the CLR/Kellogg Fellows program on an experimental basis in 1991-1992 to provide dissertation-year fellowships to six advanced doctoral students in library and information science. CLR/Kellogg Fellows for 1991-1992 were announced in June 1991. Their names, dissertation topics, and locations are:

Ann P. Bishop, "Impact of Informal Electronic Communication on R&D Work," Syracuse University

Philip Doty, "Norms of Science and Electronic Research Networks," Syracuse University

Tina Maragou Hovekamp, "Unionization as it Relates to the Employees' Work Attitudes: Work Values, Job Satisfaction, and Organizational Commitment of Professional Employees in Library Institutions," University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Dee Andy Michel, "A File Structure Model of Library Search Behavior," University of California at Los Angeles

Herbert Snyder, "A Study of the Effects of Electronic Storage of Government Information on the Freedom of Information Act: An Empirical Study with Policy Recommendations," Syracuse University

Sherry L. Vellucci, "Bibliographic Relationships Among Musical Bibliographic Entities: A Conceptual Analysis of Music Represented in a Library Catalog with a Taxonomy of the Relationships Discovered," Columbia University

Library Schools in Research Universities

The *Thirty-fourth Annual Report* described the ongoing work of the Advisory Committee on Library Education, which ended its service in November 1990. A paper summarizing the committee's findings and recommendations was published as the second part of a Council publication, *Council on Library Resources Program Reports* (December 1990). The text of that report, "Library Schools in Research Universities," is reprinted as an appendix (see page 27).

The Council has long devoted a large proportion of its funds to improving bibliographic systems and services, much of it through the now-ended Bibliographic Service Development Program. To extend the work carried out under that program, CLR established the Bibliographic Services Study Committee in 1987. A major focus of the committee's work has been the National Coordinated Cataloging Program (NCCP), a pilot project designed to test the idea that a set of libraries, working with the Library of Congress, can produce complete and accurate cataloging records to national standards, for national distribution. This important undertaking will help ensure that total national expenditures for bibliographic control will be kept as low as possible while maintaining high quality. The committee's review of NCCP, published in August 1990 as *The National Coordinated Cataloging Program: An Assessment of the Pilot Project*, is available without charge from the Council.

One important aspect of cataloging is the assignment of subject terms to describe content. The automation of large bibliographic files has greatly increased both the interest in and capability for searching for information by subject. However, the system complexity induced by subject subdivisions has become a serious handicap in automated systems, and greatly complicates the efforts of the libraries now participating in the National Coordinated Cataloging Program.

In response to these problems, a national conference was held in May 1991 to address the need to simplify subject heading practices and allow more latitude in assigning terms to describe content. The CLR-supported conference, which was attended by experts and national leaders concerned with bibliographic services, was developed by the Library of Congress staff with assistance from the CLR Bibliographic Services Study Committee and from NCCP participants. The proceedings of the conference were scheduled to be published later in the year.

CLR/National Science Foundation Project

A project begun in 1989 to explore selected aspects of scientific and engineering communication culminated with the publication of *Communications in Support of Science and Engineering* in August 1990. The report contains a discussion paper, transactions of a conference held in October 1989, a summary of the conference, a paper on uses of scientific information resources, and a report of a pilot study on library resources and research productivity in science and engineering. A limited number of copies of the report are available from the Council.

A National Engineering Information Service

The Council has been asked by the United Engineering Trustees/Engineering Foundation to assemble the individuals and resources necessary to conduct an Engineering Foundation Conference in June 1992 to explore the establishment of a national engineering information service. In June 1991, the Council engaged the services of David M. Liston, Jr., P.E., to help plan the conference.

Books for Indian Colleges

Since 1988, the Council has managed a program funded by the Pew Charitable Trusts to ship surplus books from the Exchange and Gift Division of the Library of Congress to college libraries on American Indian reservations. Over nineteen hundred books were shipped to ten colleges in fiscal year 1991. The books covered a wide range of topics, including anthropology, fiction, geography, history, medicine, and women's studies.

The principal objective of the CLR Research Program is to encourage improvement in library management by stimulating long-range planning, by supporting exploration of the interests and information needs of the scholarly community, and by encouraging analytical investigation of specific questions, especially those related to the application of computers and related technologies to information services.

During this fiscal year, the Council published a review of the CLR Research Program as the first part of *Council on Library Resources Program Reports*. The report provides an overview of the Council's Research Program activities to date: more than thirty grants and contracts, many meetings and conferences, and special studies that have contributed to program objectives.

Also mentioned in the review is a special CLR grant program, "Setting Library Policies and Priorities in Research Universities," which was announced in the spring of 1990. The impetus for the new program came from the recently completed "Statement from the Research Library Committee," which noted that the information base for teaching and learning was being rapidly transformed by integrated information technologies—computers, telecommunications, and text storage systems—but that it was far from clear how libraries and faculties would deal with digitized information and virtually unbounded means of access. It was also uncertain whether universities and their libraries would productively embrace information-age capabilities or be engulfed by them.

As a consequence, the Committee Statement concluded, universities had to undertake a fundamental rethinking of library and information service objectives, including a redefinition of the role of the research library. It further recommended that faculty and librarians should join forces to set realistic, forward-looking objectives for the research resources and services that would be needed, and should actively promote collaboration among research libraries.

Building upon these recommendations, the Council issued an invitation to research universities for proposals to undertake "policy studies and implementation planning related to future library resources and services." The announcement of the grant program

disclaimed any fixed CLR view of how a policy-setting program should be organized or which of many possible policy issues most need attention at individual universities, but it did suggest the importance of having both faculty and librarians participate, and of involving university administrators more deeply than simply approving the proposal for funds. Some flavor of the Research Library Committee's thinking made its way into the announcement in the form of specific questions the Committee had discussed, e.g.:

- What are the information requirements of various disciplines and how are they changing?
- How will access to electronic text and information services for faculty and students be managed and funded?
- What are realistic expectations for, and limits to, cooperative collecting programs among institutions?
- How will new technologies affect space requirements for collection storage?

The Council offered to make two-year grants of up to \$100,000 each, contingent upon university contribution to funding and assurance of adequate staffing as well as faculty and administration participation. Twenty-one proposals were received by the October 1990 deadline and were reviewed both by CLR staff and by external reviewers, whose recommendation was the funding of four proposals from Columbia University; Harvard University; a consortium of three universities (Duke, North Carolina State, and the University of North Carolina) called the Triangle Research Libraries Network; and the SUNY Consortium, a collaborative effort among four campuses of the State University of New York—Albany, Binghamton, Buffalo, and Stony Brook. Descriptions of the funded projects are found on pages 18-21.

CLR Grants and Contracts, 1990/1991

I. Library Operations and Planning

The Council sponsors a wide-ranging program of research and analysis concerning all aspects of library operations. Its primary aim is to consider the future form of research libraries. In practice, this has meant making grants in the areas of research, access services, and cataloging and bibliographic services. Grants made in these areas by the Council in fiscal 1991 are listed below.

1. Research

The research program concentrates on strategic planning and management issues in research libraries, broadly defined. The bulk of funds in this program area was allocated to the four grants made under the special program, "Setting Library Policies and Priorities in Research Universities," described below. All of the research grants share the common goal of providing better and more efficient service to the users of research libraries.

Special Grant Program: "Setting Library Policies and Priorities in Research Universities"

Columbia University

Objective: To examine users' and librarians' opinions about the effectiveness of current collection programs, identify alternative strategies for providing information access and delivery, estimate the costs of those strategies, and establish criteria for evaluating effectiveness of alternatives.

As the first phase in a larger institutional planning effort focused on library acquisitions and information delivery, Columbia will study information strategies in three science departments that maintain their own libraries. The three departments will include one applied

science department, one in the laboratory or life sciences, and one whose faculty interests are primarily theoretical. Against a background of heavy reliance in science upon serials whose prices are escalating, economic and organizational issues in providing electronic databases, and the likelihood of some duplication in collections as well as staffing and service costs in a decentralized system, the project will seek a better understanding of scientists' information needs and preferences, including an examination of delivery time requirements and issues in replacing print formats with electronic ones.

Harvard University

Objective: To conduct analytic studies of users' requirements, new technical capacities, and opportunities for collaboration, whose results will inform library policies and priorities.

In one study, groups of faculty, students, and library staff will identify strengths and weaknesses of the Harvard College Library, as well as the expectations and the future research and teaching needs of its users. A fundamental concern of this process is to understand how coming technological changes will affect current practices in the library and how change might be best implemented to meet scholarly needs.

Secondly, technical experts and library users will be jointly involved in a study concerned with making materials in dispersed or remote storage available through electronic record keeping, coupled with multi-channel transfer of materials by fax and high-speed data networks, in order to supplement rather than replace the physical movement of books. Finally, since innovations in storage devices, optical scanning, and electronic transmission suggest the importance of cooperative collection development and the preservation of materials, Harvard plans to explore such opportunities initially among neighboring institutions and perhaps later on a more expanded basis.

SUNY Consortium

Objective: To develop and test multi-level committee structures for planning and policy setting related to an integrated acquisitions plan for several universities in a statewide system.

The libraries at four of the State University of New York campuses (Albany, Binghamton, Buffalo, and Stony Brook) are undertaking the development of policies and plans to implement a program of cooperative collection development and resource sharing. Technological

developments make increased levels of cooperation possible among libraries. The cost of serials makes cooperation attractive. The planning activity aims to develop practical procedures for achieving institutional aspirations without needless duplication and within available resources.

The four University libraries are committed to sharing information about each other's collections and about new serial subscriptions and candidates for cancellation. They will explore joint licensing of periodical databases in electronic format, as well as the feasibility of developing an efficient, reliable, and affordable electronic delivery system. On each local campus, committees that involve library managers, university faculty, students, and senior administrative officers will oversee collection of data on serials holdings and use, study the process, and analyze policies and practices regarding resource sharing and document delivery.

***Triangle Research Libraries Network (TRLN):
Duke University, University of North Carolina, and
North Carolina State University***

Objective: To extend programmatic cooperative collection development to the sciences and electronic media, to develop mechanisms for faculty participation in information resource development, and to explore policies for collaboration in providing information service.

These three universities have long-standing programs of collaboration in collection development for print and microform materials, principally in the social sciences and humanities. The extension of these programs to electronic media and the development of new cooperative programs in the sciences require a systematic, interinstitutional, constituency-based advisory process to ensure that they are responsive to user needs.

Initially, faculty, administrators, and librarians from the three institutions will focus attention on issues of collaboration and on analytical studies of collaboration and communication among faculty; organizational and legal barriers to collaboration; overlap in collections and databases among campuses; budget models and funding mechanisms to support collaborative information resource delivery; and advisory group structures for interinstitutional collaboration. A second phase will be the execution of analytic studies whose results will influence strategies for cooperative programs and enable faculty-librarian-administrator working groups across the three campuses to

develop specific new policies and funding structures. A final phase will be dissemination of the project experience and the results of analytic studies to relevant publics.

Indiana University of Pennsylvania

Partial support to continue and extend work on enhanced subject access in online catalogs. At present, large online catalogs often yield too many or too few citations to the user. This study will focus on the development of an intelligent system that will narrow or expand the set of citations found in order to make the online catalog an effective reference tool for the user. Principal Investigator: Mary Micco, Professor, Department of Computer Science.

University of California at Berkeley

To fund a project entitled "The Humanist and the Library: Promoting New Scholarship through Collaborative Interaction between Humanists and Librarians." The aim of this project is to teach members of the humanities faculty and graduate students the capabilities of online access systems and databases, as well as the technical skills necessary to their use. This will be accomplished by grounding the educational process in working relationships between humanities researchers and professional library staff. Principal Investigators: Professor Paul Alpers, Director, and Christina M. Gillis, Associate Director, Townsend Center for the Humanities.

University of California at Los Angeles

A comparative study of the impact of technology on the structure of functional departments in three research libraries. Principal Investigator: Beverly P. Lynch, Dean, Graduate School of Library and Information Science.

University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

To fund a second Advanced Research Institute. The purpose of the Institute is to enhance the quality of research by individuals who are among the most promising and capable researchers in the field and whose focus is on questions related to the library in transition. CLR funded the successful first Advanced Research Institute in 1990. Project Director: Leigh Estabrook, Dean, Graduate School of Library and Information Science.

University of Pittsburgh

To support a study of similarities between jobs in libraries and computing centers. The researcher will develop and test a methodology to analyze and evaluate the tasks of librarians and computer specialists in colleges that have integrated their information technology. The results will be useful to college and university personnel systems in classifying jobs and compensating workers. Principal Investigator: Anne Woodsworth, Associate Professor, School of Library and Information Science.

Yale University

To establish a rapid, alternative electronic distribution system for mathematics preprints and to explore how the electronic distribution of documents affects their use. The Instant Mathematics Preprints project at Yale University seeks to establish, among interested mathematics departments at major universities, an alternative distribution system for mathematic preprints. The purpose of the project is to open the preprint distribution circuit to interested mathematicians outside current mailing lists and to ensure fast and broad communication of results, which will facilitate more direct interchange of research ideas. Project Coordinators: Katherine Branch, Head, Science Libraries, and Ronald Coifman, Professor, Mathematics Department.

2. Access Services

Improving the ability of libraries to provide access to information is a central focus of the Council. The grants described in this section contribute to the achievement of this goal.

University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

Support for a pre-survey mailing, a component of a comprehensive analysis of college and university archives in the United States. This project will update the 1980 Burkel-Cook survey of American archives. Principal Investigator: William J. Maher, Assistant University Archivist.

White House Conference on Library and Information Services

CLR funds for the 1991 White House Conference will support the preparation of delegates for their roles as state representatives through video, audio, and written instruction and will aid participants with hands-on access to the latest in information services at the conference. Project Director: Jean M. Curtis, Executive Director.

3. Cataloging and Bibliographic Services

A key element in providing equitable access is the national and international structure of cataloging systems and bibliographic services. Several projects were funded in fiscal 1991 to make that structure stronger and more efficient.

The Library of Congress

Partial support for telecommunication costs for the National Coordinated Cataloging Program. This program is aimed at coordinating the work of several participating libraries in creating MARC (MACHine-Readable Cataloging) records. Principal Investigator: Henriette D. Avram, Associate Librarian for Collections Services.

Ohio State University

To fund a study of innovative library projects (with an emphasis on expert systems) that apply cutting-edge technology to library operations. The researcher will focus on the criteria that have made these projects successful. Principal Investigator: Virginia Tiefel, Director, Library User Education, University Libraries.

University of California at Santa Cruz

To fund a study designed to capture detailed statistical information on remote usage of the Melvyl® Library System. This system is a pioneering public access catalog system that has experienced dramatic increases in use over the past few years. Principal Investigators: Terry Ellen Ferl and Larry Millsap, Librarians, University Library.

II. Librarianship

■

Many of the grants listed below are funded under the CLR Fellows Program and the Cooperative Research Program. These programs are designed to assist librarians who wish to do research connected to library operations and services, or other professional projects of importance, either alone or with other librarians or academic faculty members.

Drexel University

To fund an invitational conference of leading public library researchers and managers designed to develop an agenda for advancing the state of measurement and evaluation in public libraries. The conference focused on the critical areas of research and development in evaluation of public library performance. Principal Investigators: Thomas Childers, Professor, College of Information Studies, Drexel University, and Nancy Van House, Associate Professor, School of Library and Information Studies, University of California at Berkeley.

Maxine H. Reneker, School of Library Service, Columbia University

To fund a study that will examine by qualitative and quantitative analysis the set of information needs of members of the academic community in a research university. The relationships among characteristics of the information seeker, specific kinds of information need, the information environment as perceived by the information seeker, sources used to satisfy the need, and the factors involved in satisfying the information need will be studied.

Southern Illinois University at Carbondale

To compile a directory of international collections of children's literature in the United States. Such a directory will be useful to scholars of children's literature and to practitioners concerned with introducing multicultural materials into the classroom. Principal Investigator: Doris Dale, Professor, Department of Curriculum and Instruction, College of Education.

State University of New York at Buffalo

The investigators will undertake a survey of academic science libraries to determine the extent to which library resources are being used to provide access to nonbibliographic computer files. The number of such files used for research in the sciences is growing rapidly, and the vast majority are not accessible through commercial online vendors but are available for local mounting. This survey is aimed at increasing awareness of these materials and stimulating discussion of related collection development and service issues. Principal Investigators: Renee B. Bush, Senior Assistant Librarian, Science and Engineering Library, and William E. McGrath, Professor, School of Information and Library Studies.

Texas A&M University

To fund research aimed at establishing guidelines, procedures, and methodology for automated collection analysis and development based on the example of the business collections of the Sterling C. Evans Library at Texas A&M University. Aspects of NOTIS as an integrated library system, OCLC/AMIGOS collection analysis CD-ROM, and OCLC/EPIC service will provide assistance in the automated collection analysis and development. Principal Investigator: Suzanne D. Gyeszly, Coordinator, Social Sciences and Preservation, Sterling C. Evans Library.

Texas A&M University

To examine through statistical means the use of all currently received periodicals housed in the Current Periodicals Department and their back volumes in both paper and microformat. This study, in defining use and comparing it to factors such as subscription costs, impact factors, and relative value as reported by faculty, is intended to provide a model for use when making objective decisions concerning serials control. Principal Investigators: Marifran Bustion, Head, Serials Department, Sterling C. Evans Library, and John L. Eltinge, Assistant Professor, Statistics Department.

University of California at Los Angeles

To explore the problems associated with discrepancies in the assignment of Library of Congress subject headings. The researchers will test the hypothesis that to a considerable degree there is a correct way to assign Library of Congress subject headings and that objective measures exist for evaluating choices made by catalogers. Principal

Investigators: Elaine Svenonius, Professor, Graduate School of Library and Information Science, and Dorothy McGarry, Head of Cataloging, Physical Sciences and Technology Libraries.

University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

Support for research on the history of Argentina's National Library under the directorship of Hugo Wast, 1931-1955. Principal Investigator: Allan Metz, Assistant Professor, Latin American Library Services Unit.

Library Schools in Research Universities

Warren J. Haas

During much of 1990 an Advisory Committee on Professional Education (see page 34) assisted the Council on Library Resources in its effort to explore the problems of and prospects for the professional education of librarians. This text is the author's interpretation of the substance of the Committee's discussions and does not represent fully the views of any single member. In a real sense, it is a status report, and an incomplete one at that, with much yet to be added. It is also not a balanced report, for it concentrates on problems more than on strengths. But the problems deserve emphasis, for they are real and must be tended to if professional education is to flourish intellectually, which is, in the end, what counts.

Introduction

Not long ago, Derek Bok asserted that "education schools will continue to be relegated to the margins of university life if they do not raise the quality of their teaching and research." The evidence is strong that comparable observations are being made about library schools (witness the recent closings of several schools with long and distinguished records). It is especially disturbing that the quality and even the substance of education for librarianship is a matter of concern at this point in time, when the basic information structure on which not only scholarship and education rest, but upon which much of society depends, is in a dynamic and promising period of change. The concern of many of our most visionary educational and public leaders that the promise of the "information age" is taking shape too slowly and unevenly is, in part, a sign of frustration with librarians or, more accurately, frustration with librarianship. Justified or not (and there are many explanations for the present discomfiture), the feeling

is real. There are serious problems that need to be addressed seriously by librarians and library educators, a conclusion that is already endorsed by some and is a matter of discussion for many.

These notes summarize at least a portion of that discussion and, more important, suggest some ways of proceeding. But even at this early point, it is certain that library schools in research universities must take the lead in making needed educational improvements if librarianship as a profession is to meet personal and public expectations.

The ability of society, and of each individual, to make use of what has previously been learned or created is a matter of fundamental and enduring importance. The function of librarianship is to promote and continuously improve that ability. Librarians capable of contributing to that goal with energy and imagination are the profession's principal asset, but given the magnitude of the assignment, they are too few in number. Library schools must educate more librarians who comprehend fully the obligations of the profession and who bring to their work the exceptional range of capabilities the times require. If librarians succeed because of their education, library educators will have succeeded.

As with all critiques, the risk is great that the efforts and successes of those individuals and institutions who already sense the form of the future and are constructively at work giving it substance will be too easily overlooked. It is imperative that progress already made be recognized and enhanced, not written off in an ill-advised search for utopia.

Summary of Conclusions

1. Graduate schools in library and information science are, typically, small in faculty size and enrollment when compared with other graduate professional schools. Further, their operating budget— income and expenditures—tends to be low.

Comment: By itself, small size (but, obviously, not so small as to be non-viable) is not necessarily an insurmountable handicap, provided that the quality of the faculty is uniformly high, admission is clearly competitive, and both faculty and students are visible in and contributing to the entire university. But the reality is that schools

must find ways to expand their contributions to their universities so that their presence is felt and acknowledged. For example, undergraduate courses, whether in preparation for graduate professional education or to introduce undergraduates to the issues of personal and public importance that are implicit in the information age, need to be developed and offered. It is also essential that productive alliances be formed with the university library, both for the obvious reason that the libraries can be visible and important educational allies, and for the operational reason that each party can contribute to the performance of the other.

2. Teaching (as distinguished from research) is a principal function of all graduate library schools. It follows that the quality of teaching should be uniformly high and the course content should be centered on important and intellectually interesting issues. The academic program of library schools must be viewed as important by the university community as a whole and pertinent to the mission of the university.

Comment: While I am operating from incomplete information, this may be the most serious problem area for library schools, one requiring immediate attention. To begin, library schools in research universities should join forces in an energetic and quickly moving effort to prepare a brief, unambiguous statement on the intent and substance of graduate education in information studies. Second, each school should find ways to assure that improving the quality of teaching and the opportunities for learning are high priorities for both faculty and students.

3. While educational programs of high quality are naturally expected, the library schools in research universities have a distinctive and parallel obligation to develop and maintain the research capabilities required to press forward the frontiers of knowledge in all facets of library and information science. The research effort and its ultimate influence on practice are expected to match in quality and importance that of other university components.

Comment: In recent years, no single topic in the broad arena of information studies has had the attention accorded research productivity and quality. Development of research “agendas” has occupied federal education agencies and professional bodies with little in the way of visible results. The facts are that too little research is done, not enough that is done is distinctive and influential, and there is inad-

equate communication among researchers. The reasons are many: faculty members have heavy teaching loads, funds for research are not readily or consistently available, there are many faculty members who are not interested in undertaking research, what research there is is widely dispersed (both in and outside library schools), and there is too little productive communication between librarians and the members of the research faculties. The problem will become more serious unless appropriate corrective steps are taken, because a majority of all current tenured library school faculty members are unlikely to be teaching by the year 2000.

It is possible that, for a decade at least, an "institute for advanced information studies" should be created and operated as a collaborative enterprise and as a national base for information studies research. With imagination, funding, institutional self-effacement, and constructive leadership, such an enterprise could bring many benefits. Productive faculty from member schools would gain visibility and more opportunities for support; prospects would be improved for bringing individuals from complementary disciplines into the field of information studies (increasing the pool of potential faculty); librarians and other professionals with research interests and operating problems could be brought into a receptive intellectual setting; and doctoral and postdoctoral students would have improved prospects for support and constructive affiliation. The projected institute would have to become an integral part of each partner, not a competitor. By the same token, each member would have to contribute to the work and prestige of the institute.

4. The library schools in research universities need to assert that their principal objective is to educate students, not to train them. Virgil Hancher (one-time president of the University of Iowa) asserted his views of professional education in 1944. Nearly fifty years later, they are still sound. To paraphrase:

"Every professional student at graduation should have:

- A minimum body of basic and fundamental knowledge which is commonly possessed by members of the profession
- Skill in handling source materials and in adding to one's previously acquired body of knowledge
- The ability to think, analyze and act in the presence of a new or unprecedented situation
- An ethical attitude toward the users, to which a member of the profession may put his or her knowledge and skill.

• Finally, professional schools must stand against the illusion of practicality with which professionalism cloaks itself...narrow expertness inhibits creativity and adaptability in ways our society can ill afford. [Professional education must] enable graduates to continue to learn throughout life.”

Comment: The implications of taking this step and then following through are many and important. Admissions, student quality, faculty capabilities, the curriculum, program length, etc., will all be affected. Libraries will also be forced to give serious attention to the matter of internships and training capabilities. Most of all, it will end ambiguity about the purpose of professional education.

5. The demographic characteristics of library school students reported by Heim and Moen¹ and the motivating factors or habits of students, practitioners, and educators discussed by White and Mort² do not present an inspiring picture of professional vitality. Put simply, all components (schools, libraries, and even students) tend to follow the path of least resistance. If it weren't for visible exceptions to the norm, prospects for improvement would be bleak, but there are many notable exceptions—first-rate students, imaginative and effective faculty, demanding and progressive employers. The challenge is to make the exceptions the new norm.

Comment: Promising individuals need to be identified earlier and pressed to complete their education in their twenties so that they have the years ahead for a full professional career; employers need to rethink the composition of their staffs and demand educational credentials that reflect the importance of the work; library schools need to specify additional credentials for admission and expectations for graduation. If admission to the profession is ritualistic rather than intellectually demanding and substantive, the profession itself will be seen as one of little consequence. Practicing librarians are very influential in shaping the pool of applicants. A major target in improving the composition of the pool of applicants to library schools must be the best practitioners.

1. Heim, Kathleen M., and William E. Moen. *Occupational Entry: Library and Information Science Students' Attitudes, Demographics and Aspirations Survey*. Chicago: American Library Association, 1989.

2. White, Herbert S., and Sarah L. Mort. "The Accredited Library Education Program as Preparation for Professional Library Work." *Library Quarterly* 60, no. 3 (July 1990).

6. The generic librarian—i.e., librarians with a basic professional education but no substantive knowledge of any subject field or an important area of specialization—will be increasingly at a disadvantage in many large or specialized library settings. It seems likely that formal specialized education will be required in information technology, in the management of library systems and other information service organizations, in the structure and analysis of knowledge, and in information organization and information services for broad subject fields—requiring, in turn, in-depth understanding of pertinent academic disciplines. Basic education, for an increasing number of students, should be supplemented by a full program in a specialty that may take a year or more to complete and that, in some circumstances, might be undertaken in collaboration with a research library.

Comment: The core of knowledge of information studies needs to be reconsidered; it is not simply a synthesis of what libraries do. Even the general library education program needs to emphasize issues rather than procedures. The complexity of professional obligations and responsibilities has greatly increased in recent years and will continue to do so in the future. Library operating performance, and the work of individuals who depend on libraries, will be greatly affected by the skills and abilities of librarians. The case could be made that many current library problems stem from a shortage of well-trained professionals with distinctive capabilities in areas of primary importance.

7. Librarianship (a generic term meant to include the full range of information service organizations and information management functions) lacks definition and cohesion in the public mind and even in professional circles. Until there is a well-articulated and widely understood definition of the profession, making improvements in recruiting, funding, and even performance will be handicapped.

Comment: The introduction to this paper addresses this matter and even proposes a simple definition: “The function of librarianship is to promote and continuously improve the ability of society, and of each individual, to make use of what has previously been learned or created.” This may, or may not, offer an approach to a full definition, but it is essential that educators and working professionals join forces not only to shape a modern—and credible, easily comprehended—definition but to give the definition meaning. If library schools are to adjust their objectives and methods, the understanding and endorse-

ment of the professional community will be essential. Library schools must find ways to foster a long-term and constructive affiliation with the profession itself.

8. If the library schools of research universities are to take the lead in recasting library education and building an influential and credible research program, an all-out collaboration of the strongest schools is required to enhance and reinforce even the most ambitious institutional efforts.

Comment: Consolidation of strengths offers the only realistic prospect for success in making fundamental, long-term improvement in professional education. An opportunity exists to invigorate the profession, but it will require great effort by first-rate institutions and individuals—faculty and academic officers alike—with a personal commitment to librarianship in all its forms.

Program Committees and Project Participants

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Program Guidelines and Grant Application Procedures

The Council on Library Resources supports work by individuals and organizations on matters pertinent to library service and information systems, with the primary objective of improving the quality and performance of academic and research libraries. Individuals with specific interests and expertise are encouraged to take the initiative and propose for consideration projects within the broad areas of the Council's program, as described in this report.

In addition, the Council sponsors several competitive programs, including the CLR Fellows program, the Cooperative Research program, and the Academic Library Management Intern Program. These programs are described in brochures available from CLR.

Application Procedures

Initial inquiries should state the purpose of the proposed work, indicate methodology, establish the credentials of the responsible individuals, and provide an estimate of total costs and funding requirements. CLR will respond promptly with an indication of interest. If subsequent exploration seems justified, preparation of a complete proposal will be suggested.

Full documentation should include:

1. A concise description of the proposed project.
2. A thorough explanation of the work to be done, including objectives and methods to be employed. A timetable, pertinent background information, and plans for evaluation of results should also be provided.
3. A detailed budget linking costs to project components.
4. Curricula vitae of the principal investigators.

Proposals are carefully reviewed by CLR staff and, when necessary, external advisors, who consider such matters as relevance to current CLR interests and activities; relationship to other, similar work; projected costs in the context of the work described; and

importance of anticipated results. The Council also looks for evidence of institutional support, including cost sharing. With the exception of a few cyclical programs, there are no submission deadlines.

Support is not provided for construction or renovation, collection acquisitions, routine operating costs, activities judged to be of limited influence, or work that essentially repeats previous research. CLR does not fund indirect costs or, with rare exceptions, equipment purchases. While CLR, in consultation with its advisors, often initiates and promotes work in program areas, exploratory correspondence and conversation are always welcome, and all proposals receive careful consideration.

All inquiries should be addressed to Council on Library Resources, 1785 Massachusetts Avenue, N.W., Suite 313, Washington, D.C. 20036.

Active Projects
Financial Statements

Grants and Contracts Active in Fiscal 1991 (unaudited)

	FY 1991			
	Unpaid 6/30/90	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/91
<i>American Library Association</i>				
<i>Chicago, Ill.</i>				
Standards for ethical conduct for rare book, manuscript, and special collections librarians	\$ 5,000	\$ -0-	\$ -0-	\$ 5,000
Think tank on the uses of online catalogs	1,775	(708)	1,500 (433)	-0-
<i>Trudi Bellardo</i>				
<i>Washington, D.C.</i>				
History of online information retrieval systems	100	-0-	100	-0-
<i>Brigham Young University</i>				
<i>Provo, Utah</i>				
Prototype of a non-damaging book return unit	2,500	-0-	2,500	-0-
<i>Columbia University</i>				
<i>New York, N.Y.</i>				
Measuring the public services impact of an online catalog	11,200	(11,200)	-0-	-0-
Recasting scientific information delivery	-0-	100,000	50,000	50,000
1991-92 CLR/Kellogg Fellowship	-0-	16,000	16,000	-0-
<i>Commission on Preservation and Access</i>				
<i>Washington, D.C.</i>				
General support	133,333	-0-	66,666	66,667
<i>Cornell University</i>				
<i>Geneva, N.Y.</i>				
Core literature research in horticulture from 1850-1950	500	-0-	-0-	500
<i>Jeffrey Alan Douglas</i>				
<i>Galesburg, Ill.</i>				
American Antiquarian Society/ CLR fellowship	475	-0-	475	-0-

	FY 1991			
	Unpaid 6/30/90	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/91
<i>Drexel University</i>				
<i>Philadelphia, Pa.</i>				
Invitational conference on public library effectiveness	-0-	16,760 (575)	16,185	-0-
<i>Franklin & Marshall College</i>				
<i>Lancaster, Pa.</i>				
Preservation and collection management at liberal arts college libraries	480	-0-	-0-	480
<i>Harvard University</i>				
<i>Cambridge, Mass.</i>				
Conference on research trends and library resources	500	(790)	(290)	-0-
Strategic planning process	-0-	100,000	50,000	50,000
<i>Indiana University of Pennsylvania</i>				
<i>Indiana, Pa.</i>				
Hypermedia for improved subject access	-0-	15,000	15,000	-0-
Improving subject access in online public access catalogs	5,000	-0-	5,000	-0-
<i>International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions</i>				
<i>The Hague, Netherlands</i>				
IFLA Fellows program -				
1989-92	40,000	-0-	-0-	40,000
1990-91	40,000	-0-	40,000	-0-
<i>Johns Hopkins University</i>				
<i>Baltimore, Md.</i>				
Knowledge management: expanding the scholarly role of research libraries	132,808	-0-	-0-	132,808
<i>Kent State University</i>				
<i>Kent, Ohio</i>				
Comparison of online and manual search capabilities of students	1,000	-0-	1,000	-0-
<i>Library of Congress</i>				
<i>Washington, D.C.</i>				
National Coordinated Cataloging Program	-0-	16,299 (10,866)	5,433	-0-

	FY 1991			
	Unpaid 6/30/90	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/91
<i>National Agricultural Library</i>				
<i>Beltsville, Md.</i>				
Development of a computer-assisted instructional program for cataloging	25,084	-0-	20,000	5,084
<i>National Information Standards Organization</i>				
<i>Gaithersburg, Md.</i>				
Development of an American national standard for hardcover edition bindings	4,536	(4,536)	-0-	-0-
<i>OCLC Online Computer Library Center</i>				
<i>Dublin, Ohio</i>				
Increasing the accessibility of Library of Congress subject headings in online bibliographic systems	3,700	(3,700)	-0-	-0-
<i>Ohio State University</i>				
<i>Columbus, Ohio</i>				
Examining innovation in academic libraries	-0-	3,100	3,100	-0-
<i>Maxine H. Reneker</i>				
<i>Palo Alto, Calif.</i>				
Information seeking among members of an academic community	-0-	4,500	4,000	500
<i>SKP Associates</i>				
<i>New York, N.Y.</i>				
Evaluation of the Cataloging in Publication Program	-0-	25,000	12,500	12,500
<i>Jocelyn Sheppard</i>				
<i>Washington, Pa.</i>				
American Antiquarian Society/CLR fellowship	627	(152)	475	-0-
<i>Simmons College</i>				
<i>Boston, Mass.</i>				
Field test of the Library of Congress's "Training the Trainer" Course	949	(1,683)	(734)	-0-
Symposium on solutions to the problems of recruiting, educating, and training cataloging librarians	1,300	(114)	1,186	-0-

	FY 1991			
	Unpaid 6/30/90	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/91
<i>Southern Illinois University</i>				
<i>Carbondale, Ill.</i>				
International directory of children's literature	-0-	4,599	4,000	599
<i>Stanford University</i>				
<i>Stanford, Calif.</i>				
Economic analysis of scholarly periodical costs	2,800	-0-	2,800	-0-
<i>State University of New York</i>				
<i>Buffalo, N.Y.</i>				
Study of access to non-bibliographic computer files in academic science libraries	-0-	3,000	3,000	-0-
Cooperative Planning Grant	-0-	100,000	50,000	50,000
<i>Syracuse University</i>				
<i>Syracuse, N.Y.</i>				
1991-92 CLR/Kellogg Fellowship	-0-	16,000	16,000	-0-
1991-92 CLR/Kellogg Fellowship	-0-	16,000	16,000	-0-
1991-92 CLR/Kellogg Fellowship	-0-	16,000	16,000	-0-
<i>Texas A&M University</i>				
<i>College Station, Tex.</i>				
Automated collection analysis and development in a business collection	-0-	2,245	-0-	2,245
Comparison of journal use to reported relative value, college discipline, and subscription cost	-0-	3,000	3,000	-0-
<i>University of Alabama</i>				
<i>Tuscaloosa, Ala.</i>				
Book on library education	2,300	-0-	-0-	2,300
<i>University of California</i>				
<i>Berkeley, Calif.</i>				
The Humanist and the Library	-0-	24,000	20,000	4,000

	FY 1991			
	Unpaid 6/30/90	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/91
<i>University of California</i>				
<i>Los Angeles, Calif.</i>				
1991-92 CLR/Kellogg Fellowship	-0-	16,000	16,000	-0-
Elucidation and validation of the knowledge used by reference librarians	1,330	-0-	-0-	1,330
Objectivity in evaluating subject heading assignment	-0-	810	810	-0-
Research program: long-range strategic planning for libraries and information resources in research universities	147,424	(134,881)	12,543	-0-
Technology and structure of research libraries	-0-	4,600	3,600	1,000
<i>University of California</i>				
<i>Santa Cruz, Calif.</i>				
Remote use of the library system	-0-	2,367	2,367	-0-
<i>University of Colorado</i>				
<i>Boulder, Colo.</i>				
Information-seeking behavior of scientists	600	(2)	598	-0-
<i>University of Illinois</i>				
<i>Urbana, Ill.</i>				
Advanced research institute	2,007	-0-	2,007	-0-
Advancing research on the library in transition	-0-	28,786	22,000	6,786
CIC task force on mass deacidification	6,000	-0-	6,000	-0-
Study of searching strategies on CD-ROM	17,512	-0-	15,000	2,512
Developing and evaluating online catalog interface enhancements	2,000	(464)	1,536	-0-
A history of Argentina's National Library under the directorship of Hugo Wast, 1931-1955	-0-	4,000	3,500	500
Survey of college and university archives in the United States	-0-	1,300	1,300	-0-

	FY 1991			
	Unpaid 6/30/90	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/91
<i>University of Kentucky</i>				
<i>Lexington, Ky.</i>				
Revision of the <i>Guide to the Library of Congress Classification</i>	1,000	-0-	1,000	-0-
<i>University of Michigan</i>				
<i>Ann Arbor, Mich.</i>				
Joint education and research program	5,000	-0-	5,000	-0-
<i>University of North Carolina</i>				
<i>Chapel Hill, N.C.</i>				
Cooperative information resources development	-0-	100,000	50,000	50,000
1991/92 CLR/Kellogg Fellowship	-0-	16,000	16,000	-0-
Study of the organizational review process in research libraries	412	(1,343)	(931)	-0-
<i>University of Oklahoma</i>				
<i>Norman, Okla.</i>				
Career and communication patterns of academic librarians	2,936	-0-	2,936	-0-
<i>University of Pittsburgh</i>				
<i>Pittsburgh, Pa.</i>				
An advanced institute for government archivists	25,676	(22,294)	3,382	-0-
Examination of the effects of integrating information technology on job classification and compensation systems	-0-	18,560	17,000	1,560
<i>University of Redlands</i>				
<i>Redlands, Calif.</i>				
Diffusion of technological innovations in libraries	500	-0-	500	-0-
<i>University of Rhode Island</i>				
<i>Kingston, R.I.</i>				
Study of replacement needs for library school faculty	850	-0-	-0-	850

	FY 1991			
	Unpaid 6/30/90	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/91
<i>University of South Carolina Columbia, S.C.</i>				
Study of the knowledge and skills required for health information professionals	4,830	-0-	-0-	4,830
<i>University of Toronto Toronto, Ontario, Canada</i>				
Information retrieval systems and their users	14,000	-0-	9,000	5,000
<i>White House Conference on Library and Information Services Washington, D.C.</i>				
1991 White House Conference on Library and Information Services	-0-	15,000	15,000	-0-
<i>Yale University New Haven, Conn.</i>				
Instant mathematics preprint project	-0-	9,000	7,500	1,500
Training support for the institution of self-managing teams within technical services	2,400	-0-	2,400	-0-
<i>Current year adjustments; other refunds and adjustments from prior years' grants and contracts</i>	\$ -0-	\$ 89,147 (95,632)	\$ (6,485)	\$ -0-
<i>Totals</i>	\$650,444	\$787,073 (288,940)	\$658,899 (8,873)	\$498,551

Report of Independent Accountants

To the Board of Directors
Council on Library Resources, Inc.

Coopers
& Lybrand

We have audited the accompanying balance sheet of Council on Library Resources, Inc. (the Council) as of June 30, 1991, and the related statements of revenue, expenses and changes in fund balances, cash flows and functional expenses for the year then ended. We previously audited and reported upon the financial statements of the Council for the year ended June 30, 1990, which condensed statements are included for comparative purposes only. These financial statements are the responsibility of the Council's management. Our responsibility is to express an opinion on these financial statements based on our audit.

We conducted our audit in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards. Those standards require that we plan and perform the audit to obtain reasonable assurance about whether the financial statements are free of material misstatement. An audit includes examining, on a test basis, evidence supporting the amounts and disclosures in the financial statements. An audit also includes assessing the accounting principles used and significant estimates made by management, as well as evaluating the overall financial statement presentation. We believe that our audit provides a reasonable basis for our opinion.

In our opinion, the financial statements referred to above present fairly, in all material respects, the financial position of Council on Library Resources, Inc. as of June 30, 1991, and the results of its operations and its cash flows for the year then ended in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles.

Washington, D.C.
September 6, 1991

A handwritten signature in cursive script that reads "Coopers & Lybrand".

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

Balance Sheet

June 30, 1991

(with comparative totals for 1990)

	<u>1991</u>	<u>Totals 1990</u>
ASSETS		
Cash and cash equivalents (Note 2)	\$ 474,660	\$ 790,269
Investments (Note 2)	2,897,461	3,099,468
Grants receivable (Note 2):		
Unrestricted	—	300,000
Restricted	—	409,900
Other assets (Note 6)	88,403	94,529
	<u> </u>	<u> </u>
Total assets	<u>\$3,460,524</u>	<u>\$4,694,166</u>
 LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCES		
Accounts payable and accrued expenses	\$ 16,646	\$ 38,739
Grants and contracts payable (Note 2):		
Unrestricted	133,141	205,473
Restricted	365,410	444,971
Deferred revenue (Note 2):		
Unrestricted	300,000	600,000
Restricted	244,095	907,192
	<u> </u>	<u> </u>
Total liabilities	1,059,292	2,196,375
Fund balances:		
Designated by Board of Directors (Note 2)	79,889	1,623
Undesignated	2,321,343	2,496,168
	<u> </u>	<u> </u>
Total fund balances	2,401,232	2,497,791
	<u> </u>	<u> </u>
Total liabilities and fund balances	<u>\$3,460,524</u>	<u>\$4,694,166</u>

The accompanying notes are an integral part of these financial statements.

***Statement of Revenue, Expenses
and Changes in Fund Balances***

for the year ended June 30, 1991
(with comparative totals for 1990)

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	<u>Restricted</u>	<u>Totals 1991</u>	<u>Totals 1990</u>
Revenue (Note 2):				
Grants and contracts	\$ 300,000	\$665,536	\$ 965,536	\$ 649,124
Interest	291,638	—	291,638	324,332
	<u>591,638</u>	<u>665,536</u>	<u>1,257,174</u>	<u>973,456</u>
Expenses (Notes 2, 4, 5 and 6):				
Program:				
Research	14,189	475,853	490,042	277,990
Access	42,517	(1,116)	41,401	36,414
Bibliography	113,565	—	113,565	55,849
Librarianship	185,073	190,799	375,872	268,005
Library resources and preservation	22,989	—	22,989	21,243
Total program expenses	378,333	665,536	1,043,869	659,501
Administration	309,864	—	309,864	293,398
Total expenses	688,197	665,536	1,353,733	952,899
(Deficiency) excess of revenue over expenses	(96,559)	—	(96,559)	20,557
Fund balances, beginning of year	2,497,791	—	2,497,791	2,477,234
Fund balances, end of year	<u>\$2,401,232</u>	<u>\$ —</u>	<u>\$2,401,232</u>	<u>\$2,497,791</u>

The accompanying notes are an integral part of these financial statements.

Statement of Cash Flows

for the year ended June 30, 1991

(with comparative totals for 1990)

Cash flows from operating activities:
(Deficiency) excess of revenue over expenses
Adjustments to reconcile (deficiency) excess of revenue over expenses to net cash (used in) provided by operating activities:
Amortization of investment (discounts) premiums
Decrease in grants receivable
Decrease in other assets
Decrease in deferred revenue
Decrease in accounts payable and accrued expenses
Decrease in grants and contracts payable
Total adjustments
Net cash (used in) provided by operating activities
Cash flows from investing activities:
Purchase of investments
Sale of investments
Net cash provided by (used in) investing activities
Net (decrease) increase in cash and cash equivalents
Cash and cash equivalents, beginning of the year
Cash and cash equivalents, end of the year

The accompanying notes are an integral part of these financial statements.

<u>Unrestricted</u>	<u>Restricted</u>	<u>Totals 1991</u>	<u>Totals 1990</u>
\$ <u>(96,559)</u>	\$ <u>—</u>	\$ <u>(96,559)</u>	\$ <u>20,557</u>
1,311	—	1,311	(11,494)
300,000	409,900	709,900	1,027,260
6,126	—	6,126	21,020
(300,000)	(663,097)	(963,097)	(439,224)
(22,093)	—	(22,093)	(16,073)
(72,332)	(79,561)	(151,893)	(264,162)
<u>(86,988)</u>	<u>(332,758)</u>	<u>(419,746)</u>	<u>317,327</u>
<u>(183,547)</u>	<u>(332,758)</u>	<u>(516,305)</u>	<u>337,884</u>
(1,089,404)	(409,900)	(1,499,304)	(1,804,674)
<u>957,342</u>	<u>742,658</u>	<u>1,700,000</u>	<u>1,800,000</u>
<u>(132,062)</u>	<u>332,758</u>	<u>200,696</u>	<u>(4,674)</u>
(315,609)	—	(315,609)	333,210
<u>790,269</u>	<u>—</u>	<u>790,269</u>	<u>457,059</u>
\$ <u><u>474,660</u></u>	\$ <u><u>—</u></u>	\$ <u><u>474,660</u></u>	\$ <u><u>790,269</u></u>

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

Statement of Functional Expenses

for the year ended June 30, 1991

(with comparative totals for 1990)

	<u>Research</u>	<u>Access</u>	<u>Bibliography</u>
Unrestricted:			
Grants and contracts	\$ 4,600	\$16,300	\$ 81,341
Refunds and overappropriations	(411)	(1,343)	(59,605)
Staff and travel	—	6,088	17,667
Advisory committees, consultants and interns	10,000	1,266	35,024
Board expenses	—	—	—
Support services including office expenses	—	20,206	39,138
	<u>14,189</u>	<u>42,517</u>	<u>113,565</u>
Restricted:			
Grants and contracts	495,347	—	—
Refunds and overappropriations	(139,067)	(1,588)	—
Staff and travel	33,947	—	—
Advisory committees, consultants and interns	39,198	472	—
Support services including office expenses	46,428	—	—
	<u>475,853</u>	<u>(1,116)</u>	<u>—</u>
Total expenses	<u><u>\$ 490,042</u></u>	<u><u>\$41,401</u></u>	<u><u>\$113,565</u></u>

The accompanying notes are an integral part of these financial statements.

<u>Librarianship</u>	<u>Library Resources and Preservation</u>	<u>Total Program Expenses</u>	<u>Administration</u>	<u>Totals 1991</u>	<u>Totals 1990</u>
\$ 24,834	\$ —	\$ 127,075	\$ —	\$ 127,075	\$ 112,882
(1,948)	(4,536)	(67,843)	—	(67,843)	(132,164)
61,567	6,053	91,375	151,369	242,744	235,046
18,524	1,266	66,080	—	66,080	90,054
—	—	—	42,031	42,031	31,400
<u>82,096</u>	<u>20,206</u>	<u>161,646</u>	<u>116,464</u>	<u>278,110</u>	<u>266,557</u>
<u>185,073</u>	<u>22,989</u>	<u>378,333</u>	<u>309,864</u>	<u>688,197</u>	<u>603,775</u>
164,652	—	659,999	—	659,999	248,613
(80,441)	—	(221,096)	—	(221,096)	(86,370)
—	—	33,947	—	33,947	41,726
106,197	—	145,867	—	145,867	103,401
<u>391</u>	<u>—</u>	<u>46,819</u>	<u>—</u>	<u>46,819</u>	<u>41,754</u>
<u>190,799</u>	<u>—</u>	<u>665,536</u>	<u>—</u>	<u>665,536</u>	<u>349,124</u>
<u>\$375,872</u>	<u>\$22,989</u>	<u>\$1,043,869</u>	<u>\$309,864</u>	<u>\$1,353,733</u>	<u>\$952,899</u>

Notes to Financial Statements

1. Organization

The Council on Library Resources, Inc. (the Council) is a non-profit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1956 for the purpose of promoting library research.

The Council's operations are financed through unrestricted general support grants and through several restricted grants from private foundations and other sources. The Council conducts its work through directly administered projects as well as grants to and contracts with other organizations or individuals.

2. Summary of significant accounting policies

The significant accounting policies followed in the preparation of the financial statements are described below:

Basis of accounting

The financial statements of the Council have been prepared on the accrual basis.

Grant revenue

Grants to the Council are recorded in the balance sheet as grants receivable and as deferred grant revenues when awarded. Revenues of restricted grant funds are recognized only to the extent of expenditures that satisfy the restricted purposes of these grants.

Unrestricted grant revenue is recognized as income in accordance with the budgeted annual payments specified by the grantors.

Grants and contracts payable

Grants and contracts made by the Council are recorded in the balance sheet as grants and contracts payable and as an expense at the time recipients are awarded the grants. Current period expenses are reduced for grant or contract refunds or over appropriations when received.

Cash and cash equivalents, and investments

Cash and cash equivalents consist primarily of deposits in a money market mutual fund. Investments which consist of treasury notes are recorded at amortized cost which approximates market. These balances include restricted amounts of \$609,505 and \$1,352,163

at June 30, 1991 and 1990, respectively. Cash equivalents represent investments with original maturities of 90 days or less and, therefore, bear minimal risk. Interest which is not restricted by the related grants is recognized as unrestricted revenue.

Functional allocation of expenses

Costs of providing the various programs have been summarized on a functional basis in the accompanying financial statements. Certain indirect costs identified as support services costs have been allocated directly to programs and administration on a systematic basis. These costs primarily include salary, benefits, rent and other expenses.

Board designated funds

Pursuant to resolutions of the Board of Directors, designated funds were established in a prior year.

3. Income taxes

The Council, a private operating foundation, is exempt from Federal income tax under Internal Revenue Code section 501(c)(3) and applicable regulations of the District of Columbia.

4. Retirement plan

Employees are eligible for participation in the Council's defined contribution retirement annuity program (the Plan) administered through the TIAA/CREF insurance companies. Individual contracts issued under the Plan provide for full and immediate vesting of both the Council's and employees' contributions. The Council's contribution, net of that reimbursed by the Commission on Preservation and Access (the Commission), was approximately \$49,000 in fiscal year 1991.

5. Commitments

The Council has entered into a noncancelable lease agreement for office space which expires in May 1993. The minimum future rental due will be approximately \$172,000 per year through May 1993. As part of this lease agreement, the Council will be assessed an annual charge based on its proportionate share of the increase in the operating costs of the building. For the year ended June 30, 1991, rent expense totaled \$137,000, of which approximately \$5,500 represents

the Council's share of the increase in the operating costs.

The Council subleases a portion of its leased office space. Rental income from this sublease amounted to approximately \$35,000 in fiscal year 1991.

6. Commission on Preservation and Access

The Commission on Preservation and Access (the Commission) is a non-profit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1988 for the purpose of fostering, developing, and supporting systematic and purposeful collaboration in order to ensure the preservation of the published and documentary record in all formats and provide equitable access to that information. In 1989, the Council granted to the Commission \$2,067,000 it had received on behalf of the Commission for support of the Commission's preservation program. Also, in 1989, the Council awarded to the Commission a general support grant totaling \$200,000 of which \$66,667 was payable to the Commission at June 30, 1991.

The Council also entered into an agreement with the Commission effective July 1, 1988 under which the Council provides office space, employee services including employee benefits, equipment, supplies and other overhead items to the Commission. Commission staff members are employees of the Council and receive the same benefits as members of the Council. A percentage of shared overhead costs, which is negotiated annually, was charged to the Commission. For fiscal year 1991, the Commission's share was 25%, or \$94,400. The total amount of direct expenses of \$292,200 and other overhead costs of \$94,400 were charged to the Commission for fiscal year 1991. At June 30, 1991, the Commission owed the Council \$26,739 under the terms of this agreement.

Certain members of the Council's Board of Directors are also members of the Commission's Board of Directors. However, as these members are in the minority and there are no other elements of managerial or financial control, these two entities have not been combined.

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